

US and Them - Ethnic tensions and nationalism in Latvia

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Abstract: Nationalism in Latvia has played a very important role in the history of the country and continues to be a driving force in domestic and foreign politics today. Modern day politics and decisions are often justified with unrelated historical context and certain interpretations of historical events. The Soviet period in Latvia resulted in a high ratio of ethnic Russians, as much as 40% of the entire population by some estimates, and has over time produced a highly split society along these ethnic lines. These ethnic lines are often also politically dividing. With increasing radicalization and potential conflicts in the post-Soviet era due to ethnic tensions, it is highly likely to see societal and political tensions grow over time. As it stands, the trends in society, politics and academia are not conducive to any attempts to consolidate the society by compromise or understanding, nor does there appear to be any will to do so. This presages an uncertain future for Latvia and the region as a whole.

Keywords: nationalism, Latvia, Russia, ethnic tensions

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Introduction

After the restoration of Latvia's independence in 1991, and the country had begun to develop and stabilize, a wide range of ideas and ideologies started to circulate in the public, fueled by either opportunistic power grabs or promotion of previously illegal or fringe philosophies. For most of these ideas, and the people behind them, it was essential to compete for public support and self-promotion, in particular when it comes to highly nationalistic ideas. These were more often than not based on antagonism against the previous Soviet leadership, now embodied by a newly formed Russian Federation. Many of them did indeed manage to grow into full-fledged organizations, at times reviving old organization names or using some form of reference to organizations or individuals from the past.

During this time ideas expressed by political parties and organizations invariably center upon nationalistic ideology as much as they do on economic issues. Ethnic tensions within the state, which are their root of many societal issues, are nearly always justified with callbacks to the Second World War and the events that followed after it. For example, the

Soviet occupation of Latvia, mass deportations, russification policies etc. The very concept of nationalism is becoming particularly relevant in public discourse during the pre-election period. In the rhetoric of Latvian political parties, organizations, society and the media there is a specific and clear division of forces between “right” and “left”. Not in line with the theoretical spectrum of party ideological affiliation, this is peculiar development in Latvia, forming a division between the representatives of ethnic groups rather than traditional ideology - Latvian nationalists on one side and advocates, supporters and representatives of national minorities, most notably Russian-speakers, on the other. Supporters of nationalistic ideas in this case generally, although not without exception, tend to belong to the “right” side of the political spectrum, often motivated by ethnic nationalism ideas and exclusivity, as well as historical resentment towards specific minorities. It has to be noted that a significant part of non-Latvian people, ethnic minorities that could not demonstrate Latvian heritage or pass the language examination, do not hold Latvian citizenship and thus do not have voting rights. Despite of that, political forces exist that advocate for them and cater to them. These, unsurprisingly, are often accused of being funded by foreign powers and promoting their interests.

Political parties and nationalist organizations themselves have developed and changed a lot over the course history since their creation. Again, the post-Soviet period is marked with increased presence of Latvian nationalism in society and for the first-time parties with such ideology are actually in charge of state policy, and not merely exist as underground or fringe organizations subverting foreign rule or engaging in armed insurgency. Given the rapid development and ever changing of nationalistic organizations and parties over time, it is important to take a closer look at some of the more politically significant and impactful of them and the general situation in a historical context, in order to build a picture of developing trends and what possible future dangers, if any, may arise. Post-Soviet space overall has not remained stable even 30 years after the collapse. Animosity between countries and within parts of society within each country are in a state of constant tension, and the newly independent nations have found themselves in the middle of a global and domestic power struggle and identity crisis.

Historical context for Latvian nationalism and the origin of the Anti-Russian sentiment

Historically, Latvian nationalism has developed over a period of over 150 years and can be divided into multiple stages. Spanning from the first ideas of Latvians as an ethnicity and distinct culture in the mid 19th century, through to the interwar period, the Soviet period and to the modern day. At different times the emphasis between ethnic and political nationalism has shifted, as it has between different groups and organizations during any particular time. The most significant periods in the history of Latvian statehood are called *Nacionālā Atmoda*, meaning National Awakening, of which there are three, split by the Soviet period between the second and third, with the last one resulting in the restoration of Latvia as an independent state at the end of the Soviet collapse. Over the last 25 years in Latvian society, having one the largest ethnic Russian minorities among post-Soviet European countries, tensions have routinely been heightened over a number of domestic and international events.

The birth of Latvian modern nationalism in historical literature traditionally dated to the 1850s, since that decade saw several important developments for Latvian national identity. In 1856, the first known book of Latvian national poetry was published, demonstrating that the Latvian language is capable of producing literary works on par to those of other nations. But more importantly, 1856 marked the first publication of the newspaper *Mājas Viesis* in Riga - the first newspaper in Latvian language. The attitude of *Mājas Viesis* towards the national idea was expressed in the poem published in its first issues that roughly translates into: “We are Latvians! And with that name we will live forever, friends. Whoever dares to tread on the honor of our nation, will regret it forever.”[1] Publication of the newspaper created social upheaval and confusion among the ruling Baltic German elites, and also harsh action against it. The very existence of a newspaper, the content of which is determined by a Latvian, was considered as something unnatural, abnormal, impossible in the existing social order. The affiliation of the newspaper's authors and editors with the Latvian people and

their national consciousness determined the overall national orientation of the newspaper and the range of issues it covered. The priority of the newspaper was the needs of Latvians at that time - creation of Latvian national identity. To promote this, the newspaper also contained other valuable educational articles that contributed to national, societal, and economic development. The idea of emancipation of the people was based on pursuit of education, national pride, development and promotion of Latvian language and literature, as well as a developed economy and increasing wealth.[2] *Mājas Viesis* was a communication channel for the idea of Latvian national identity and social values. The newspaper became the first Latvian national public outlet through which concept of the nation has become geographically and socially widespread among Latvians.

The next event in the development of the national movement was the establishment of a new newspaper. This time in St. Petersburg, where a large part of Latvian intellectuals lived, hence it became as the place of publication a Latvian newspaper, which was also hoped to be less restrictive in terms of publishing and censorship. The new newspaper - *Pēterburgas Avīze* received its funding from wealthy Latvians and other private donations. The newspaper's task was also to raise awareness of Latvian readers about modern society and to help get rid of the many social notions that were still in their minds. The original idea of the newspaper was to act as the means of public communication between Latvian intellectuals and common people, and promote the movement of self-definition of Latvians as a nation and as individuals, and, at the same time, promote the inclusion of Latvians in the world economic and socio-political processes. The newspaper was first published on July 14th, 1862, and the pages of the first fifteen issues were filled with publications of public value and promotion of national identity. The situation changed when the newspaper was first censored because of widespread public response and caused dissatisfaction among the highest representatives of the Baltic elites who feared an uprising. They also got the newspaper banned for four months in 1863. Following the resumption of activities, the editorial office of the newspaper abandoned the propaganda of the idea of emancipation and nationalism, and the content was increasingly made up of popular and educational articles. On June 17th, 1865, the newspaper was officially discontinued.[3]

The central government of the Russian Empire purposefully sought to strengthen its domestic political influence in the Baltic provinces through internal affairs with the help of the governors appointed by the minister, which were independent of the Baltic German nobility and directly subordinate to the governor. There was a radical increase in the role of the Russian language in public administration and the education system, particularly in the 1880s. The original intention was that education and training would only be conducted in Russian. However, that did not succeed as both Latvians and the Baltic German nobility and clergy were opposed to it and didn't follow the rule. Under the new rules, almost all education had to take place only in Russian, and Latvian was not allowed to be used even for communication in any formal setting, which was to be enforced with various penalties. In practice, however, in schools did not follow this rule as it was not practically feasible to enforce it, and complying with the new rules was largely left at the discretion of local teachers. While the ability to speak multiple languages certainly had its benefits, an attribute most Latvians still have today, professionally, it also meant that any Latvian who would become successful would work in an environment where his native language was not being used. But this language hierarchy did also directly contribute to the growing national awareness.[4]

At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century the territory of modern day Latvia experienced rapid economic development, especially in the fields of manufacturing, transit and commercial services. Demand for labor in fast-growing cities caused the labor market to explode with opportunity, along with wages increasing multiple fold. The population of Latvia had doubled in the last 50 years to at least 2.5 million by 1914. The biggest part of the growth took place at the beginning of the 20th century, the level of urbanization in the territory of Latvia reached levels

comparable to European and American levels. The population of cities increased both at the expense of the rural population and because of immigration from other regions of the Russian Empire. Latvian cities were not only relatively large but became highly multi-ethnic and multicultural in nature. There wasn't, and still isn't, a single city or town in Latvia that was not ethnically diverse. The city of Riga grew particularly fast, becoming the fourth largest city in the Russian Empire and major trading port. Rapid growth was driven by domestic economic policies of the Russian Empire, which promoted development and investment in manufacturing and advanced industry. This also encouraged foreign investment in the Russian Empire, and the Baltic area was one of the most convenient for placing factories, having easy access to much of Europe. A factor just as significant was the relatively high level of education of the local population compared to other areas of the Russian Empire.

Following a brief period of independence as a result of the fall of the Russian Empire in 1918, Latvia once again became the part of a Russian dominated state at the beginning of the Second World War. Already in the first days of the Soviet occupation in 1940, the services of the NKVD and the Red Army started arrests of the citizens of the still formally independent state and prepared deportations of those arrested. The leading officers of the Latvian Armed Forces were arrested and sent to prison camps without due process, and the Latvian court system was completely ignored. Immediately after the occupation, the legislation of the USSR was introduced that targeted so-called "enemies of the people", which were also to be arrested and deported. The deportations took place mainly on the basis of social class and those who had been deemed to engage in "counter-revolutionary" activities and "anti-Soviet agitation", as well as the wealthiest citizens of the former Republic of Latvia. Among those arrested were many rural residents and land owners who were repressed mainly for security reasons. The deportation of women, children and the elderly was based on the arrest of the head of the family. The deportation of more than 15,000 Latvians took place on June 14th 1941. The families that were deported were first sent to railway stations, where the men were separated from their families and sent to a camp in Smolensk, Russia. Women, children and the elderly were deported to camps in Krasnoyarsk Krai, Novosibirsk area and northern Kazakhstan, where they had to work mainly in logging and on collective farms.[5]

Already after the first weeks of losing independence, militant groups began to form among the more patriotic and nationalistic people, growing into underground resistance organizations made up of former guards, youths, and others who did not wish to accept the Soviet occupation. The Soviet authorities managed to detect and liquidate most of these groups, which were mainly engaged in the distribution of anti-Soviet leaflets, fairly quickly. Others turned more militant, the best known resistance groups were Brīvā Latvija (Free Latvia) and Latvijas Nacionālais Leģions (Latvian National Legion).

From 1944 through to 1945 the Red Army advanced on the territory of Latvia and retook it from German forces who had been there for several years. Repressions against supporters of Germany began almost immediately, and for the third time in five years the nation was subjected to a complete political purge and restructuring. After the Second World War the Latvian National Partisans, also known as Forest Brothers, opposed the authorities of the Latvian SSR, largely consisting of former Latvian soldiers from German units who refused to surrender in 1945. As before, passive and intellectual resistance was more common as a large number of illegal anti-Soviet leaflets and newspapers were being published during the first couple years after the war, before the people behind them got arrested and prosecuted.[7]

In March of 1949, the Soviet Union commenced a large-scale repression and deportation operation. As a result of it more than 42,000 Latvians were deported to labor camps in Siberia and Far East regions of the Soviet Union. In return, immigration from the USSR was encouraged, marking the beginning of the russification policy. The targets of the deportation were landowners and their families, family members of known partisans and other dissidents, as well as known families who engaged in anything that could be perceived as anti-Soviet activities. Since the decision was to deport whole families, more than a quarter of the deportees were children under 16 years of age. To facilitate the deportation

an additional 4,500 troops were brought in from Russia.[8] In 1950 a small group of intellectuals formed an organization called Franču grupa (the French group), whose purpose was not to do any real damage to the Soviet regime, but, allegedly, to exist merely as a discussion group. However, just within a year of its creation the Soviet authorities arrested most of its members for participation in anti-Soviet meetings. The members of the group were sentenced to 7 to 25 years in prison and deportation to USSR settlements in Siberia. The aim of the repressions was to isolate people disloyal to the regime and to intimidate the Latvian intelligentsia and act as a deterrent for others.[9]

By the early 1950s the National Partisan units increasingly faced weapon and ammunition problems. Over time, the Soviet authorities managed to destroy or capture a large part of the partisans and their supporters as they could no longer maintain an armed resistance. The KGB also successfully infiltrated their networks and supplied information that led to the capture of fighters. The 1949 deportations also significantly affected public support for the partisans. People feared deportations and prison sentences if seen or suspected of aiding the partisans. According to the Soviet estimates, the number of fighters had dropped from an initial estimate of around 20,000 in 1944-1945 to less than 100 by 1953. In 1959 the last Forest Brothers surrendered due to futility, lack of weapons and amnesty promised by the Soviet leadership.[7]

The following decades, until 1980s, were marked by strong and effective russification efforts and there are virtually no organizations or active resistance to the Soviet regime. During this time Latvian nationalism was mostly concentrated in Latvian communities overseas, mainly in the United States and Canada, consisting of families of war time refugees and their communities. These, however, had no impact on the situation in Latvia itself until after the restoration of independence.

March 16th Latvian SS legionnaires day.

Perhaps no two events highlight the irreconcilable differences between Latvians and ethnic Russians and their view of historical events as much as the commemoration of the Latvian SS troops, generally favored by Latvian nationalists and opposed by Russian speakers, and the Soviet-associated May 9th Victory Day celebrations, which the Latvians in turn consider a day celebrating the Soviet occupation of Latvia.

The Remembrance Day of the Latvian SS Legion in 1998 became the first public confrontation of social memory and different interpretations of the past in Latvia. This also gained a wider international reaction, and created open confrontations between Russians and Latvians. Strong condemnation of the memorial procession in Riga was expressed by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation, saying that the Latvian Legion has taken part in punitive actions and its history is marked by the blood and suffering of many people. The favorable attitude of Latvian officials towards legionnaires was especially criticized, claiming that it is a shame for Europe, a challenge to the memory of the many millions of victims of war, and it is emphasized that Latvia's ruling circles actually agree with the forces that cultivate nationalism and russophobia in society.[10] The events of March 16th in Riga were reported in foreign media, especially in the Russian Federation, claiming that fascist Holocaust perpetrators march in Latvia and that we are witnessing the reemergence of fascism, and with the full support of the Latvian government at that. On March 26th, 1998, Helmut Kohl, the German chancellor at the time, also said that there has been a National Socialist demonstration in Latvia.[11]

Along with these events, the Latvian nationalist parties advocated the inclusion of the Latvian Legion Memorial Day as a national holiday. At the March 12th, 1998 parliamentary session the right leaning Latvian nationalist TB/LNNK faction proposed to mark March 16th as the Latvian SS Legion remembrance day. Although at the Commission on Human Rights and Public Affairs this proposal was not supported, and the parliament considered the issue of the Latvian Legion Memorial Day at its sitting on May 7th, 1998. Consequently, the proposal for the inclusion of this day in the list of national days of remembrance was rejected. During the discussions it was suggested that this day could be celebrated

as a general day of remembrance for Latvian soldiers instead, formally omitting its direct affiliation with the SS Legion. It was supported by a number of parties, and the TB/LNNK group submitted a proposal to mark March 16th as Remembrance Day of Latvian Soldiers. This time it was also supported by the Commission on Human Rights and Public Affairs. In practice, however, this did not change the point of the holiday, instead it provided more justification to associate and portray the Latvian SS Legion with freedom fighters who fought for Latvian independence rather than people drafted or into a foreign army or willingly joined it.

Since 1998 the day has become an argument and battle between different political opinions and different interpretations of history. Already in the following years of 1999 and 2000 a rather tense situation was observed, which shed light on people's response to the day and what it celebrates. Opponents of the Legion Memorial Day organized trips to Riga from other towns across Latvia and while a service was held in the Dome Church in memory of the former legion soldiers. The Russian community in Latvia was organizing a protest at the Congress Hall in Riga. The participants of the protest chanted and sang self-composed songs depicting the former legionnaires and the government.[12]

While some Holocaust and prosecution victims, and Red Army veterans have expressed their forgiveness to their former enemy and their desire for a Latvian society that would live in mutual respect and tolerance. However, this is not a very widespread attitude as no efforts have been actually made to distance the soldiers themselves as human beings and victims of happenstance and war, which are the ones who are officially commemorated, from the institutions, army, symbols, uniforms and events associated with them and the SS Legion as a whole.

The memorial procession for the Latvian Legion does not limit itself to an annual confrontation in downtown Riga. It has gradually become an important part of Latvian society, emphasizing the deep divide in it and the differing interpretations of historical events. The Soviet system with the strict oppressive policy of the Latvian people appears to have left a deep cultural trauma on the collective Latvian consciousness, and determines their actions and decisions. Evidently, in a society like that it is difficult to create stable and reliable values, clear definitions of past events nor to move on from them. A singular event of the past has become the defining attribute by which all current decisions are made. Such a situation cannot be healthy, but evidently the society has nothing else to grab onto or to identify with that would put them in opposition to what they consider their enemy.

The Memorial Day of the Latvian Legion seemingly has done nothing but divide society into supporters and opposition. In a survey conducted by SKDS in 2008 shows that 43.6 percent of the public supported the celebration of the day, but 31.6 percent oppose it. Moreover, this division is strongly correlated with ethnicity that each individual identifies with. The majority of those who support it identify as Latvian and the majority of those who oppose it identifying as Russian.[13]

May 9th Soviet victory day celebrations

The collapse of the Soviet Union led to a drastic change in rituals and symbols in all former Soviet republics. In Latvia May 8th became the official Victory Day and the day of remembrance for the victims of the Second World War, which was changed from May 9th. It demonstrated the will to integrate into the European political culture, where the day of remembrance and remembrance of the victims has always been May 8th. However, for parts of the Latvian population, primarily the Russian speaking part, May 9th as the Victory Day of the Soviet Union survived and continued with an annual celebration tradition. Since 1991 the meaning of Victory Day has undergone significant transformation in Latvia

and plays an important role in the political scene. For Latvian nationalists it is a symbol of Soviet occupation, but for the Russian minority it is an event that celebrates their cultural and ethnic identity more than anything.

The perception of Victory Day was further influenced by changes in societal attitudes towards the Soviet period and rise of Latvian nationalism, combined with resentment towards Russian speakers by the various organizations that label all Russians living in Latvia as an occupying force or descendants thereof. Due to its rather tragic and complex history, there are many memorial sites and a soldiers' cemeteries from all involved countries and nationalities that are part of Latvian historic and cultural environment and social memory. The past war still reminds of itself when alarming news reports appear about wartime explosive ordinance and weapons found in the Latvian countryside, in the woods, also near houses, sometimes even in their foundations, attics and elsewhere.

Official remembrance of the victims of the Second World War and its victims takes place annually on May 8th, with its main venue being Riga Brothers' Cemetery, where the ceremony is attended by the President, the Prime Minister, Speaker of the Parliament, ministers, representatives of the military, foreign diplomats and other officials. The public attendance at these events has generally been quite small. In a survey conducted in 2010, 83.9% of respondents admitted that they had not celebrated the Day of Destruction of Nazism and the Day of Remembrance of the Victims of the Second World War on May 8th in the last five years. This attitude shows that a large part of the Latvian population is not clear about the significance of this event in the history of the world or Latvia.[14]

Cemeteries of Soviet soldiers and the memorials dedicated to the Second World War are the main historical and political symbols of the Latvian Russian-speaking community. In Latvia the politicization of the Victory Day is began in the second half of the 1990s and coincides with the rise of nationalism in both the Latvian and Russian-speaking population respectively. In later years pro-Russian Latvian politicians started to appear more and more often at the Victory Monument on May 9th. Starting with the 7th parliamentary elections in 1998, the pro-Russia political party For Human Rights in a United Latvia (PCTVL) took on the role of organizers of the festival. Later, the efforts of PCTVL gradually lead to the popularity of the Harmony Center, another pro-Russian party. When in 2003 the reform of Russian schools began and the importance of learning the Latvian language was increased, large protests were directed against the reform. The Victory Monument in Riga and similar memorials in other major cities of Latvia became a symbolic space where the Russian community could exercise their political activity and identity.[15]

Over years the debate over May 9th celebrations has been growing, as have verbal and physical conflicts surrounding it. Each year the day comes with thousands of people gathering around the Victory Monument and the nearby park, singing wartime songs and flying red flags. In general, the attitude of the Latvian population towards the day is split in half, essentially among the lines of ethnicity. This is especially evident in towns and cities with a higher proportion of Russian-speakers in the south-east of the country. Overall, the day itself has become a symbol of the Russian-speaking community and of Soviet legacy. Quite often the day also coincides with other protests, such as school reforms for minorities, and citizenship issues. To this day, most people who do not have a Latvian ethnic background and immigrated to the country during the Soviet period do not have Latvian citizenship, and thus also no right to vote. Victory Day in Latvia gradually transformed into a symbolic solidarity event between former Soviet citizens and the Russian community.

To some extent the May 9th Victory Day holds a symbolic meaning in the Russian community that can be compared to the Song and Dance Festival in the Latvian community - an event that is also a key cultural identifier. Russians and Latvians living in Latvia are actually not that different in terms of ethnic culture, the whole conflict is entirely political and is based on perspectives of historical events of the 20th century, especially during the Second World War and the subsequent actions of the Soviet regime. For Latvians it is a time of abuse and military occupation even after the official

end of war, hence the hesitance to commemorate it. On the other side, for Russians it is culturally and politically considered a triumph and achievement for the Soviet Union. For many ethnic Russians living in Latvia it is psychologically difficult to accept the very fact of occupation of Latvia and insisting on the liberation narrative because its recognition forces them to accept an unfavorable point of view of themselves and the Soviet period.[16] In addition, people who ended up in a newly independent Latvia after the Soviet collapse found themselves in a severe identity crisis as their legal, political and cultural status was changed overnight. Russian scholars likewise concur that overinflated Soviet-era identities and national pride had collapsed along with self-glorifying interpretations of historical events, and people were for the first time confronted with opposite ideas, leaving people without a real identity.[17] During the Soviet era, Russians became the dominant ethnicity in Latvia, serving as its instrument of russification, affecting administration, economy, public services, educational and media infrastructure, as well as Soviet commemorative culture and mythology. Latvian culture and history were and remained foreign to the Russians living in Latvia even after the collapse of the USSR, and they appear to have formed their identity based on it.[16]

The Russian-speaking community of Latvia has a tendency to self-isolate from the Latvian community in terms of cultural and political aspects, and prefers to maintain a connection with the Soviet Union and the Russian Federation instead. The prevalence of Russian media in Latvia, especially in the space of television broadcasts appear to perpetuate and facilitate this.[18] Nationalism of the Russian-speaking population of Latvia is influenced by the resurgence of nationalism in Russian Federation. Its conception of history is centered on pride in Russia and the role of the Russians in the history of mankind, especially the victory of the USSR in the Great Patriotic War and, according to their view, liberating numerous countries. This invariably puts them at odds with Latvian nationalists who in turn see Latvia as a victim of Soviet occupation, not liberation. The arrival of the Soviet army in Eastern and Central Europe in 1944–1945 is considered by modern Russia as liberation of the peoples of Europe. This view has also strengthened among Russian-speakers in Latvia allows to ignore the fact of the Soviet occupation of Latvia and the abuses of Latvians. It may also contribute to the idea that the Baltic states are to be an area of exclusive Russian influence to this day, whether by historical claim or by the number of Russian-speakers living there. This has resulted in many claims and worries of Russian political meddling in Latvia's internal affairs by various means, such as media and funding of political forces.

Large-scale Victory Day celebrations in Riga, and other parts of the country, promoted the ethnic consolidation of Latvia's Russians, at the same time putting the Soviet victory in the war as the cornerstone of their social identity. In a survey conducted at the end of 2010, asking: "What the most significant event in the history of Latvia in the 20th century?", 30.5 percent of Russian-speakers in Latvia indicate that it was the Soviet victory in the Second World War. Other Latvian past events, such as gaining independence in 1918, in their view, are not able to compete with Soviet victory in terms of significance.[19] It is this sense of pride and achievement of the Soviet period that promotes political solidarity among Latvia's Russians and its conflict with ethnic Latvians, especially Latvian nationalists. Nowhere is this better exemplified than in the media coverage of May 9th events at the Victory Monument.

Initially, during the first years after restoration of independence, May 9th celebrations got relatively little attention, and when they were mentioned they generally tended to be mentioned in a way that would distance the day from the people in general. For example, in 1991, the newspaper *Diena* title for May 9th coverage was "Armed forces in Riga celebrate their holiday", the armed forces at the time still being the Soviet military or remnants thereof.[20] The emphasis on the ethnic origin and political affiliation of the event participants remains in the content and titles of publications to this day. However, developments and type of celebrations of May 9th that have attracted media attention have developed a gradual shift to the day and the people as a political and social issue rather than a day of commemoration for the victims of the war. The names of publications in newspapers are a clear indication of the change in the May 9th representation. During the first 15 years of independence the coverage tended to be fairly neutral, for example, in 2000, *Diena*

published an article with the title "Veterans Celebrate Victory Day", but since around 2005 that took a rather sharp turn and the titles and content became more and more expressive - "Victory Day is celebrated by singing and drinking", "Picnic at the Foot of the Monument", etc. In 2009, Latvijas Avīze and Neatkarīgā Rīta Avīze did the same, portraying the event as a strictly Russian event with a tangible amount of discontent and animosity - "Imperial Russian Picnic in Riga" and "May 9th unfolds with a picnic of Russian-speaking solidarity". Headlines most often include the aspect of the publication that may be most interesting to the consumer. They usually use expressive language - in order to evoke a vivid imagination and present a certain depiction of the event. This is especially relevant when looking at Latvian media coverage regarding Victory Day celebrations in recent years. They generally follow a very clear "us and them type" of narrative, and the representation of "them" is universally ironic and demeaning, thus indicating their insignificance and further perpetuating societal fragmentation.

Victory Day celebrations is also one of the ways in which Russia can influence the people of Latvia. This is largely not only due to the Russian media presence in Latvia, but also traditions and practices established during the Soviet period, which in their current format are so strong that many overshadow Latvia's public holidays. In particular events surrounding the interpretation of the Second World War show that there are almost irreconcilable differences between Latvians and Russians. In the current politicization are likely to increase during periods of domestic political activity, such as the parliamentary and municipal elections.

In relation to the May 9th Victory Day celebrations the parliament supported the ban on the display of Georgian ribbons in public events, as proposed by members of the National Alliance faction in 2021. Members of the pro-Russian "Harmony" party, as well as a number of non-aligned members, voted against the ban. The ban on the public display of Georgian ribbons, or the Ribbon of Saint George, at public events includes amendments to two bills - the Law on the Security of Public Entertainment and Festivities and the Law on Meetings, Processions and Pickets, and resulted in the inclusion of the ribbon in the "forbidden symbols" list. The amendments envisage supplementing the existing ban on the use of clothing identifying the flags of the former USSR, uniforms of former USSR and Nazi Germany, their armed forces and law enforcement agencies, coats of arms and anthems, Nazi swastika, the SS insignia and Soviet symbols - a sickle and a hammer with a five-pointed star. These symbols may only be displayed where their use is not for the purpose of glorifying totalitarian regimes or justifying criminal offenses, or is used for educational, scientific or artistic purposes.[21]

The celebration of Victory Day of the Soviet Union is still the main symbolic conflict between Latvia and Russia, as well as the Latvian and Russian-speaking community within Latvia today. This is rooted not only in the differing interpretations of history, but also in the desire for conflict by of parts of the Russian-speaking community and Latvian nationalists alike. For both May 9th closely associates with the Soviet period and present-day Russia, but on completely opposite sides.

Language and politics

As one might expect, the deep rooted ethnic tensions are very evident in the Latvian political arena. In terms of political representation there is generally a fairly extensive representation of Latvian nationalist type parties as each one tries to emphasize their "Latvianess" more than the other. While over the years many have combined into larger and more powerful organizations, there is still significant lack of cooperation and individual desire for power that perhaps limits the reach and impact they may otherwise have. On the other side is the pro-Russian political force. As opposed to the Latvian nationalist parties this is a very united entity, and currently there is just one - the Latvian Russian Union. Their

representation in politics is very limited but socially they are quite prominent. This is primarily because a very significant number of ethnic Russians living in Latvia do not have voting rights.[22]

In 2004 tensions in society rose when the Cabinet of Ministers developed and approved new State Language Policy guidelines. The guidelines go beyond the legal framework language policy as it was and are already regulating language usage in areas like public communication, business and education language use and compel minorities to learn and use the official state language in day to day activities.[23] Since 1989 Latvian language policy is based on two basic principles; one is that the official language in Latvia is Latvian, second is that the state guarantees the possibility for Latvian minorities to use and practice their native language and culture. These basic principles of the state language policy are also clearly defined within the Language Law itself:

- 1) "to create a mechanism for ensuring the competitiveness of the Latvian language and its priority is the highest in all socio-linguistic functions, as is the protection of the linguistic rights of the Latvian speaker;
- 2) to guarantee the possibility to preserve, develop and use Latvian minority languages in certain functions.[24]

However, it does not clearly specify what those functions may be, which leaves a lot of ambiguity to when a person is permitted to use a minority language in communication or promote it.

In 2005 the Ministry of Education and Science of Latvia fully committed to transitioning to bilingual education in minority schools. This meant that ethnic minority children, often struggling with the Latvian language, would now be forced to take most classes and examinations in Latvian, which is a foreign language to them. This caused a series of protests and opposition from organizations and individuals supporting Russian schools in particular, which considered this new policy as specifically targeting and discriminating the Russian minority.[25] It was argued that this would seriously undermine the quality of education received by Russian children and this would compromise their competitiveness in the labour market, the ability to access universities and obtain scholarships, which are judged by centralized examination results, since the exams are also to be taken in Latvian. Publications in the news media and public polls from that period showed that the use of Latvian among non-Latvians had become to be viewed sharply negative. However, after a compromise on the proportion of languages of tuition in schools was reached, and various support activities for minority teachers were also organized, such as the release of tutorials and guidance materials and Latvian language improvement courses, attitude towards Latvian in every-day communication and its use in education improved. The compromise ratio of subjects was set at 60% in Latvian and 40% could remain in Russian for an unspecified period of time.[26]

In 2018 the Cabinet of Ministers agreed to a new education reform beginning in 2019. This new reform included a gradual transition to Latvian as the sole language of tuition in all ethnic minority secondary schools and increase the percentage of general subjects taught in Latvian in ethnic minority elementary schools to at least 50% for grades 1–6 and 80% for grades 7–9. The only exception being their respective native language, literature and subjects related to culture and history of the ethnic minorities that will continue to be taught in the respective minority languages.[27]

The new controversial bill proposed extending the same language restrictions of 2004 to apply to all public higher education institutions and to private universities and colleges as well. This meant that private higher education institutions beginning from September 1st 2019 will not be allowed to enroll new students in study programs taught in non-official languages of the European Union, such as, for example, Russian. The bill was opposed by some parties in the government, predominantly the ones which are seen as pro-Russian leaning, as well as the heads and academic staff of some universities and NGOs.[28] In response to the new reforms the State Duma of the Russian Federation released a statement strongly objecting to the reform and claiming it violates the principles observed by most civilized countries, and

demanded for special economic measures to be taken against Latvia. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Russia warned that the new legislation will have a negative impact on Latvian–Russian relations.[29] Attempts were made to dispute the bill in court on the grounds that it violates the Constitution of Latvia regarding the protection of ethnic minorities and their ability to freely practice and promote their language and culture. However, the court dismissed the plea.[30] The reform also saw a series of protests from a large number of Russian speakers gathering outside the Ministry of Education and Science and other public areas, numbering a few hundred to over a thousand each time, but these were universally dismissed and portrayed as being politically motivated and funded from abroad, hinting at Russia.[31]

In the first half of 2019, the research agency SKDS conducted a survey on the attitude towards the reform among the inhabitants of Latvia. Overall 41.4% of respondents supported the motion and 34.7% opposed it, however, the results showed a significant polarization of opinions, depending on the language spoken at home. Of those who spoke Latvian at home almost 60% expressed either full or partial support for the reform, whereas 64% of respondents speaking Russian at home said they were partially or completely against the motion.[32]

Conclusion

Nationalism and ethnic tensions in Latvia have become a particularly heated issue over the last several years, fueled by different interpretations of past events and grudges, over acts committed by people who are long gone. Historically, Latvian nationalism is extremely complex, spanning nearly two centuries of development, with only about a quarter of that time Latvia existing as an independent state, split into two periods by 50 years of the Soviet rule. So it comes as no surprise that Latvians may harbor some historical resentment for past events, but more importantly - modern day politics are often framed and justified with a historical context even if the issue itself may not actually be related to anything that happened in the past.

At the start of the Second World War, as a result of an agreement between the Soviet Union and Germany, Latvia, like several other small nations, was to be included in the Soviet Union and the Soviet army occupied the territory of Latvia in 1940. Overall there was no significant military resistance and the leadership of Latvia complied with the Soviet ultimatum in order to save the lives of Latvians, realizing that armed resistance is futile. Given how soon after the formation of the Latvian state this was, many people were still born in the Russian Empire, and this may explain why initially there was quiet acceptance. This, however, changed drastically as the new Soviet leadership immediately commenced political repressions and deportations of anyone who opposed them. It is quite likely it was this moment that placed the seed for the resentment of Russians for the future, making it a cornerstone of Latvian nationalism.

The Soviet period is arguably the most significant in shaping current day society and politics in Latvia. The Soviet deportations and repressions are among the most tragic dates commemorated in Latvia, yet it is interestingly omitted from Latvian history books that Russians were likewise subjected to gulags and repressions by the millions. One can speculate what the motivation for that might be, but indeed most Latvians today only associate repressions and deportations as something done to them by Russians, not as something done to millions of people of all backgrounds by an authoritarian government. It would not be unreasonable to assume that such a formulation, one of many, of history, as it is being taught in schools, is deliberate.

By late 1990s and early 2000s nationalist parties were the most prominent in Latvian politics. It was also at this time when some of the most controversial policies were made and anti-Russian sentiment began to grow. Radical nationalist organizations at this time were very disorganized and vocal, although did not manage to draw in many supporters. May 9th Victory Day began to be seen as a holiday of the occupier - the Russians. March 16th was established as a Latvian SS Legion Memorial Day, drawing in large protests and police stand offs every year. For some they are Nazi regime collaborators, for others - freedom fighters. These two days alone split the public in half and create animosity

among regular people based on ethnic background. Likewise, May 9th sees almost exclusively negative press coverage in Latvian media, and the Soviet built Victory Monument was even subjected to a bombing by far-right nationalists.

Additionally, Latvian leadership targeted Russian schools in an education and language law reform, ending state supported education in Russian. It is important to note that about 40% of Latvia's population are ethnic Russians or speak Russian as their mother tongue. Every time the next step in the reform was taken, teachers and students from Russian schools would flood the streets by the thousands in protest. The constitution of Latvia actually states that minorities have a right to obtain education in their native language and that they are allowed to promote and practice their culture. However, this is left pretty vague and it does not clarify that the state has any obligation to actively facilitate this right, such as providing education in a minority language. As a result of the shift in language of instruction, Russian speaking students saw a reduction in their academic performance, which subsequently affected their ability to get admission into universities and colleges. Signage using the Cyrillic alphabet was also prohibited under the language laws, including for private businesses. Note that signage in any other foreign language is allowed and widely used.

Overall, there are important conclusions that can be made by following the development of Latvian nationalism and its current status and possibly predict future developments:

1) The whole concept of Latvian nationalism in its present form is rooted in resentment and historical injustice. From originally restoring their culture and independence, Latvian nationalism has turned into something where hatred against Russia and Russians, often regardless of their individual beliefs political views, has become its primary identifying attribute;

2) The society has become almost completely divided along ethnic lines due to a continuous push for conflict by the means of collective memory and historical interpretation. The main tool in this is Latvian state media that continues to present ethnic Russians living in Latvia as something akin to a foreign occupying force or remnants thereof. The headlines of May 9th coverage demonstrate how the presentation and perception has become increasingly hostile;

3) Opposing interpretations and discussions of history and current events are prohibited in an arguably unconstitutional manner. As it stands, nearly all discourse on the more controversial issues is not accepted neither by society nor by academia for purely political reasons. Specifically relating to the Second World War and current situation in Ukraine. As of 2022 Latvian citizens have actually been arrested and jailed for covering Ukraine events on their social media accounts, and expressing opinions not in line with the state narrative;

4) No efforts to reconcile or understand the perspective of each other are made by neither Russian nor Latvian nationalists. With the increased presence in governance, Latvian nationalists appear to continuously implement more and more policies that the ethnic Russian minority considers a direct attack on their rights. The ultimate end goal of that is unclear, but as mentioned before - so far all that has achieved in an ever growing ethnic division in society.

All in all the situation of Latvian nationalism appears to become more divisive and tense over time with no clear path of reconciliation, common ground or mutual understanding and acceptance of differences.

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